

VEKTORLARNING TENGLAMALARNI YECHISH VA TENGSIZLIKLARNI
ISBOTLASHGA TADBIQLARI**Bulakova Feruza**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu tezisdagi vektorlar nazariyasining asosiy xossalari yordamida ba'zi irratsional tenglamalarni yechishning va tengsizliklarni isbotlashning sodd usuli keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Kollinear vektorlar, Koshi-Bunyokovskiy tengsizligi, irratsional tenglamalar, tenglamaning ildizi.

Geometriya fani qadimiy tarixga ega bo'lib, unga oid boshlang'ich tushunchalar bundan 4000 yil ilgari Misr va Bobilda vujudga keladi. Geometrik bilimlarning vujudga kelishi odamlarning amaliy faoliyati bilan bog'liq. Qadimdayoq geometriya aksiomalar sistemasiga asosan tuzilgan qat'iy mantiqiy fanga aylangan. U uzluksiz rivojlanib yangi teoremlar, g'oyalari va usullar bilan boyib borgan. Ko'pincha matematikani boyitgan yangi tushunchalar fizika hamda kimyo va tabiatshunoslikning ayrim bo'limlaridan kelib chiqadi. Masalan, vektor tushunchasi mexanikadan olingan. Shuning uchun vektorlar nazariyasi amaliyotda muhim tadbirlarga ega. Xususan, amaliy matematika va matematik modellashtirish masalalarini sodd usulda yechishda, matematik tengsizliklarni isbotlashda, geometrik masalalarni yechishda vektorlarning xossalari keng foydalaniladi [1]. Shuningdek, vektorlar nazariyasi tushunchalari yordamida algebra va geometriyaning bir qancha misol va masalalarini yechish mumkin. Xususan, vektorlar nazariyasiga asoslangan koordinatlar usuli, Li metodi va bir qancha usullar mavjud. Geometriyaning rivojlanishida XVII asrda fransuz matematigi va filosofi Rene Dekart ishlari tufayli vujudga kelgan koordinatlar usuli muhim ahamiyatga egadir [2-3]. Quyida ushbu tadbirlarning biri hisoblangan vektorlar nazariyasi asosida tenglik va tengsizliklarni isbotlash va yechish usullari keltirilgan.

1. Tengsizliklarni isbotlash.

Ushbu usul yordamida tengsizliklarni isbotlash uchun tengsizlikda qatnashgan o'zgaruvchilar vektor koordinatalari sifatida qaraladi va vektorlar xossalari foydalaniladi.

1-misol. Quyidagi Koshi-Bunyokovskiy tengsizligini isbotlang[4]:

$$(a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + a_3b_3)^2 \leq (a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2). \quad (1)$$

Bu yerda $a_1, a_2, a_3, b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \mathbb{R}$.

Yechimi. Ko'rinib turibdiki, agar $a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 = 0$, $b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2 = 0$ bo'lsa, (1) tengsizlik o'rinli. Faraz qilaylik, $a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 \neq 0$, $b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2 \neq 0$ bo'lsin. U holda, quyidagi ikki vektorni qaraymiz:

$$\vec{a}(a_1, a_2, a_3), \vec{b}(b_1, b_2, b_3), |\vec{a}| \neq 0, |\vec{b}| \neq 0.$$

Ma'lumki, ushbu vektorlar uchun quyidagi tengliklar o'rinli:

$$\begin{aligned} (\vec{a}, \vec{b}) &= a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + a_3b_3, \\ \cos\varphi &= \frac{(a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + a_3b_3)}{\sqrt{a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2}\sqrt{b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\cos^2 \varphi = \frac{(a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2 + a_3 b_3)^2}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2)}.$$

Shuningdek, $\cos^2 \varphi \in [0; 1]$ munosabatdan quyidagi tengsizlikka kelamiz:

$$\frac{(a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2 + a_3 b_3)^2}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2)} \leq 1,$$

$$\frac{(a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2 + a_3 b_3)^2}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2)} \leq \frac{(a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2)}{(a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2)}.$$

Ushbu $a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2 \neq 0$, $b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2 \neq 0$ munosabatlar o'rinli ekanligidan foydalanib, quyidagi tengsizlikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$(a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2 + a_3 b_3)^2 \leq (a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2)(b_1^2 + b_2^2 + b_3^2).$$

2-misol. Agar $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = \pi$ bo'lsa, quyidagi tengsizlikni isbotlang:

$$tg^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + tg^2 \frac{\beta}{2} + tg^2 \frac{\gamma}{2} \geq 1.$$

Yechimi. Ushbu tengsizlikni isbotlash uchun quyidagi tenglikdan foydalanamiz:

$$tg \frac{\alpha}{2} tg \frac{\beta}{2} + tg \frac{\alpha}{2} tg \frac{\gamma}{2} + tg \frac{\beta}{2} tg \frac{\gamma}{2} = 1. \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = \pi$. Dastlab (2) tenglik isbotini keltiramiz:

Dastlab, (2) tenglikka $\frac{\alpha}{2} = \pi - (\frac{\beta}{2} + \frac{\gamma}{2})$ munosabatni qo'yamiz:

$$tg \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} + \frac{\beta}{2} \right) \right) \left(tg \frac{\beta}{2} + tg \frac{\gamma}{2} \right) + tg \frac{\beta}{2} tg \frac{\gamma}{2} =$$

$$= \frac{1}{tg \left(\frac{\beta}{2} + \frac{\gamma}{2} \right)} \left(tg \frac{\beta}{2} + tg \frac{\gamma}{2} \right) + tg \frac{\beta}{2} tg \frac{\gamma}{2} =$$

$$= \frac{(1 - tg \frac{\beta}{2} tg \frac{\gamma}{2})}{tg \frac{\beta}{2} + tg \frac{\gamma}{2}} \left(tg \frac{\beta}{2} + tg \frac{\gamma}{2} \right) + tg \frac{\beta}{2} tg \frac{\gamma}{2} = 1 - tg \frac{\beta}{2} tg \frac{\gamma}{2} + tg \frac{\beta}{2} tg \frac{\gamma}{2} = 1.$$

Endi asosiy tengsizlikni isbotlashga o'tamiz.

$tg \frac{\alpha}{2}, tg \frac{\beta}{2}, tg \frac{\gamma}{2}$ haqiqiy sonlar uchun 1-misolda keltirilgan Koshi–Bunyakovskiy tengsizligini qo'llaymiz:

$$1 = \left(tg \frac{\alpha}{2} tg \frac{\beta}{2} + tg \frac{\beta}{2} tg \frac{\gamma}{2} + tg \frac{\gamma}{2} tg \frac{\alpha}{2} \right)^2 \leq$$

$$\leq \left(tg^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + tg^2 \frac{\beta}{2} + tg^2 \frac{\gamma}{2} \right)^2.$$

Demak,

$$tg^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + tg^2 \frac{\beta}{2} + tg^2 \frac{\gamma}{2} \geq 1.$$

2.Irratsional tenglamalarni yechish.

Ushbu usul yordamida irratsional tenglamalarni[5-7] yechish uchun tenglamada qatnashgan o'zgaruvchilar vektorlar sifatida qaraladi va ushbu vektorlarning skalyar ko'paytmasi qarab chiqiladi.

3-misol.Quyidagi irratsional tenglamani yeching:

$$x\sqrt{x+1} + \sqrt{3-x} = 2\sqrt{x^2+1}.$$

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Yechimi.Ma'lumki, tenglamaning argument qabul qilishi mumkin bo'lgan qiymatlar quyidagi sistema yordamida topiladi:

$$\begin{cases} x + 1 \geq 0, \\ 3 - x \geq 0, \\ x\sqrt{x+1} + \sqrt{3-x} \geq 0. \end{cases}$$

Demak, $x \in [0; 3]$.

Quyidagi ikki vektorni tanlab olamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{a}(x; 1), \vec{b}(\sqrt{x+1}; \sqrt{3-x}), \\ (\vec{a}, \vec{b}) &= x\sqrt{x+1} + \sqrt{3-x}, \\ |\vec{a}| \cdot |\vec{b}| &= \sqrt{x^2+1}\sqrt{x+1+3-x} = 2\sqrt{x^2+1}, \\ \cos\varphi &= \frac{(\vec{a}, \vec{b})}{|\vec{a}||\vec{b}|} = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Bundan kelib chiqadiki, \vec{a} va \vec{b} vektorlar kollinear. Demak,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x}{\sqrt{x+1}} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{3-x}}. \\ x\sqrt{3-x} &= \sqrt{x+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

(3) tenglikning ikkala tomonini kvadratga ko'taramiz:

$$\begin{aligned} (x\sqrt{3-x})^2 &= (\sqrt{x+1})^2, \\ x^2(3-x) &= x+1, \\ x^3 - 3x^2 + x + 1 &= 0, \\ (x-1)(x^2 - 2x - 1) &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Ushbu tenglamaning ildizlari quyidagilar:

$$x_1 = 1, \quad x_2 = 1 + \sqrt{2}, \quad x_3 = 1 - \sqrt{2}.$$

Ushbu $x \in [0; 3]$ shartga asosan, berilgan tenglamaning ildizlar $ix_1 = 1, x_2 = 1 + \sqrt{2}$ sonlardan iborat.

Endi odatiy usul bilan ham shu tenglamani yechib ko'raylik:

$$\begin{aligned} x\sqrt{x+1} + \sqrt{3-x} &= 2\sqrt{x^2+1}, \\ x^2(x+1) + 3-x + 2x\sqrt{(x+1)(3-x)} &= 4x^2+4, \\ x^2(3-x) - 2x\sqrt{(x+1)(3-x)} + (x+1) &= 0, \\ x\sqrt{3-x} &= \sqrt{x+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Bevosita tekshirish mumkinki, so'nggi tenglik (3)tenglik bilan aynan bir xil.

4-misol.Quyidagi irratsional tenglamani yeching.

$$x\sqrt{2x-1} + 2\sqrt{x-1} = \sqrt{x^2+x-1}\sqrt{2x+3}.$$

Yechimi.Tenglamaning argument qabul qilishi mumkin bo'lgan qiymatlar quyidagi sistema yordamida aniqlanadi:

$$\begin{cases} 2x - 1 \geq 0, \\ x - 1 \geq 0, \\ 2x + 3 \geq 0, \\ x^2 + x - 1 \geq 0, \\ x\sqrt{2x-1} + 2\sqrt{x-1} \geq 0 \end{cases} \rightarrow x \geq 1.$$

Endi quyidagi ikki vektorni qaraymiz:

$$\vec{a}(x; \sqrt{x-1}), \vec{b}(\sqrt{2x-1}; 2).$$

Ma'lumki,

$$\begin{cases} (\vec{a}, \vec{b}) = x\sqrt{2x-1} + 2\sqrt{x-1}, \\ |\vec{a}||\vec{b}| = \sqrt{x^2+x-1}\sqrt{2x+3}, \\ \cos\varphi = \frac{(\vec{a}, \vec{b})}{|\vec{a}||\vec{b}|} = 1. \end{cases}$$

Demak, \vec{a} va \vec{b} vektorlar kollinear. U holda

$$\frac{x}{\sqrt{2x-1}} = \frac{\sqrt{x-1}}{2},$$

$$2x = \sqrt{2x-1}\sqrt{x-1}.$$

Oxirgitenglikning ikkala tomonini kvadratga o'taramiz:

$$4x^2 = (2x-1)(x-1).$$

$$2x^2 + 3x - 1 = 0.$$

Ushbu tenglamaning ildizlarini topamiz:

$$x_1 = \frac{-3 + \sqrt{17}}{2}, x_2 = \frac{-3 - \sqrt{17}}{2}.$$

Ushbu $x \geq 1$ shartga asosan, topilgan ildizlar berilgan tenglama uchun yechim bo'la olmaydi. Bevosita berilgan tenglamani kvadratga ko'tarish yordamida soddalashtirish orqali ham berilgan tenglamaning yechimga ega emasligini tekshirish mumkin.

5-misol. Quyidagi irratsional tenglamani yeching.

$$2\sqrt{x-1} + 5x = \sqrt{(x^2+4)(x+24)}$$

Yechimi. Tenglamaning argument qabul qilishi mumkin bo'lgan qiymatlari $x \geq 1$ tengsizlikni qanoatlantiradi.

Endi quyidagi ikki vektorni qaraymiz:

$$\vec{a}(2, x), \vec{b}(\sqrt{x-1}, 5)$$

Ma'lumki,

$$\begin{cases} \vec{a} \cdot \vec{b} = 2\sqrt{x-1} + 5x \\ |\vec{a}| \cdot |\vec{b}| = \sqrt{(x^2+4)(x+24)} \\ \vec{a} \cdot \vec{b} = |\vec{a}| \cdot |\vec{b}| \end{cases}$$

Demak, \vec{a} va \vec{b} vektorlar kollinear. U holda,

$$\frac{2}{\sqrt{x-1}} = \frac{x}{5}$$

Ushbu tenglamaning ildizi $x = 5$ ga teng.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI.

- 1.B.A.Xudayarov. Chiziqli algebra va analitik geometriya. 1-qism. Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2018.
- 2.T.H.Rasulov, G'.G'.Qurbonov, Z.N.Hamdorov. Analitik geometriyadan misol va masalalar. O'quv qo'llanma.
- 3.F.Rajabov, S.Masharipova, R.Madrahimov. Oliy Matematik. Toshkent: Turon-Iqbol, 2007.

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VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

- 4.М.А.Мирзаахмедов, Ш.Н.Исмаилов, А.Қ.Аманов, В.Қ.Хайдаров. 11-синлар учун математика дarsligi. Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2018.
- 5.В.В.Арлазаров, А.В.Татаринцев, И.Г.Тиханина, Н.С.Чикалкин. Сборник задач по математике для физико-математических школ. М., 2007.
- 6.В.А.Ильин, Э.Г.Позняк. Аналитическая геометрия. М, 2012.
- 7.С.Н.Олехник, М.К.Потапов, П.И.Пасиченко. Уравнения и неравенства. Нестандартные методы решения. М., 2001.

